

Molecular Docking and ADMET Study of Selective Phytochemicals and Synthetic Drugs against (Respiratory Syncytial Virus) RSV (7LVW Fusion Protein)

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ABSTRACT

Respiratory Syncytial Viral Infection is one of the most common viral infections in the respiratory airways and is more common in infants, younger children and some adults. While ribavirin is used to treat RSV infection and various drugs are still under pipeline. Also, Structure-based drug design using Computational tools has shifted the paradigm of Drug design and its discovery. The fusion core of the Respiratory Syncytial Viral (RSV) structure is crucial for its fusion, entry and replication in the host cell. Herein, we investigated molecular Docking and ADMET parameters of Phytochemicals which are having high potential against RSV virus, also the main target of research to show that phytochemicals are highly essential and potent activity against RSV than synthetic drug which is used in market for RSV treatment. The study involve use of 7LVW protein docked with 50 ligands in that 10 ligands show promising result against RSV, also they are having high docking score than synthetic drug which means these phytochemicals can be used in prophylactic treatment of RSV. The docking score of Chebulic Acid (-6.27), Hesperdin (-5.57), Rosamarinic Acid (-6.57) Were Found To More Potential Than Sisunatovir And Ribavirin.

Keywords: Respiratory Syncytial Viral Infection, Molecular Docking, ADMET Study, 7LVW Fusion Protein.

INTRODUCTION

RSV Is Respiratory Syncytial Virus was Discovered in 1956 but it was not associated with infants, According, Morris and Co-Workers isolated a new virus called Chimpanzee Coryza agent (CCA). Later on Chanock and its co-workers confirmed that causes Respiratory illness in humans, and it was found that when specific neutralizing antibody to CCA was found to be present in most of children and CCA renamed to Respiratory Syncytial Virus (RSV).¹

The Risk of Severe Disease in Adults is increased by Chronic Pulmonary Disease, Circulatory conditions and functional Disability and with high Viral loads. RSV is a hospital-acquired Threat infection to young infants and immunocompromised. Highly Mortality Rates have been observed in those infected with RSV following bone marrow or Lung Transplantation.

RSV belongs to Genus Orthopneumovirus with the family Pneumoviridae and Order Mononegavirales There are main two types of antigenic types RSV A and B, determined largely by antigenic drift and Duplications in RSV-G sequence, but accompanied by Genome -wide sequences divergence, including within RSV-F.²

STRUCTURE OF RSV-

Fig.1-Structure of RSV

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- A nucleocapsid enclosed in a bilipid-layer envelope produced from the host membrane makes up the RSV virion.
- Virion grown in cell lines consists of long filaments up to 10 μm in length and spherical particles with a diameter of 100-350 nm.
- Three proteins make up the viral envelope: the attachment protein (G), the small hydrophobic protein (SH), and the fusion protein (F).
- The individual homo-oligomers formed by the viral glycoproteins appear as short surface spikes (11–16 nm).
- Beneath the lipid membrane is the matrix protein (M).
- The nucleoprotein (N) encases a single-stranded, negative-sense RNA that makes up the genome.
- The transcription processivity factor M2-1, phosphoprotein (P), and RNA polymerase protein (L) are still connected to the nucleocapsid.

SYMPTOMS OF RSV-

Signs and Symptoms start to appear after Five to six days after exposure of virus. It include following Symptoms-

- Congested or Runny Nose
- Dry Cough
- Low grade fever
- Sore Throat
- Sneezing
- Headache

In severe Cases it include,

- Fever
- Severe cough
- Wheezing
- Rapid breathing

- Bluish color of skin³

Epidemiology of RSV-

RSV can be dangerous, particularly in elderly and newborn patients. Individuals with compromised immune systems, older adults, premature newborns, small children with lung or heart conditions, and very young infants are among those who are more vulnerable.⁴

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A- Docking Analysis-

A-Preparation of protein crystal structure-

The X-ray crystallographic structure of 7LVW from the protein data bank and retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.2210/pdb7LVW/pdb>. The protein preparation wizard of the Glide software (Schrodinger suite) was used to rectify specific errors such as missing hydrogen in protein during X- ray crystallography. The protocol used in this study has been previously described. The bond order were assigned and possible missing hydrogen in the PDB structure were added. Also, disulphide bond created between two sulphur atom in proximity and other option were left as default. Full energetic optimization was performed in the final refinement step using OPLS3 force field and the RAMSD of heavy atom was set at 0.3 \AA .⁵

B- Preparation of library of natural compounds –

About 50 compounds from the natural origin were downloaded from IBES databases and uploaded on workspace of maestro molecular interface (11V5) of Schrodinger suite. Low energy 3D conformers with satisfactory bond length and angle of each 2D Structure were generated. The possible ionization state for each ligand structure were generated at a Physiological PH of 7.2 \pm 0.2. all other options were as kept as default and the ligands were minimized using optimal potential liquid simulation (OPSL3) forced field. The Ramchandran plot of 7LVW is Illustrated in fig.2.⁶

Fig.2-Ramchandran Plot of 7LVW

C-Site Map and Grid Generation-

The first stage of sitemap calculation is to locate the site. A site is defined by the set of site points on the grid that are either contiguous or bridged by short gaps in solvents exposed regions.

The second stage of sitemap calculation generated the various “maps” that defined the sites. The map is defined by a set of values of property on a given 3D grid.

For each site, the 5 maps- hydrophilic, hydrophobic donor, acceptor and surface are returned to file (.grd files and .vis file) that can be used by maestro to display the surfaces.

Total 12 site map are generated, out of 11th site map has a score of -1.39 which is the highest among all site map, secondly on that site map Grid was generated.

The site score was evaluated to be 1.39 which is a site of particular promise.⁷

Fig.3- Site Map and Grid Generation of 7LVW

D-Molecular Docking Studies-

The Glide grid file was generated via receptor grid generation panel by Picking the co-crystallized ligand located at the active site of the protein to automatically reveal x, y, z coordinates respectively. Glide uses the position and size of ligand to calculate a default the center and default size for the region of which grid which will be calculated.

The virtual screening of 50 compounds was carried out using 3 hierarchical GLIDE docking filtering, namely: High throughput virtual screening (HTVS), standard precision (SP) and extra precision (EP). HTVS docking is intended for the rapid screening of vast number of ligand. HTVS has much more restricted conformational sampling than SP docking, standard precision (SP) docking is appropriate for screening ligands of unknown quality in large numbers. Extra precision (EP) docking and scoring is a more robust and discriminating procedure which takes longer to run than SP. EP is design to be used on ligand poses that have been determined by high scoring using SP docking. The databases was run through SP docking. First, the top 30% of final poses was further docked using EP to score the compound binding affinity via more expensive docking simulation on worthwhile poses.

Too accurately predict the binding novel inhibitors with the protein crystal, induced-fit docking (IFD) was implemented. IFD protocol aimed to improve docking of ligand it is believed that the receptor adjust significantly to be presence of ligand the protocol perform the constraint minimization of receptor followed by initial glide docking of ligand using a soften potential. A selected set of the docked possess is passed on to prime for a refinement step. After a prime site chain prediction and minimization, the best receptor structure for each ligand are passed back to the glide for re-docking of the ligand.⁸

Table.1-IUPAC NAME and 2D structure of Lead Compounds10

Sr. no	Ligand name	IUPAC name	Structure
1	Chebulagic acid	2[(4 <i>R</i> ,5 <i>S</i> ,7 <i>R</i> ,25 <i>S</i> ,29 <i>S</i> ,30 <i>S</i> ,31 <i>S</i>)-13,14,15,18,19,20,31,35,36-nonahydroxy-2,10,23,28,32-pentaoxo-5-(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoyl)oxy-3,6,9,24,27,33-hexaoxaheptacyclo[28.7.1.0 ^{4,25} .0 ^{7,26} .0 ^{11,16} .0 ^{17,22} .0 ^{34,38}]octatriaconta-1(37),11,13,15,17,19,21,34(38),35-nonaen-29-yl]acetic acid	
2	Chebolic acid	2[(4 <i>R</i> ,5 <i>S</i> ,7 <i>R</i> ,8 <i>R</i> ,11 <i>S</i> ,12 <i>S</i> ,13 <i>R</i> ,21 <i>S</i>)-13,17,18-trihydroxy-2,10,14-trioxo-5,21-bis[(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoyl)oxy]-7-[(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoyl)oxymethyl]-3,6,9,15-tetraoxatetracyclo[10.7.1.1 ^{4,8} .0 ^{16,20}]henicosa-1(19),16(20),17-trien-11-yl]acetic acid	
3	Eugenin	5-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methylchromen-4-one	
4	Gaultherin	methyl 2-[(2 <i>S</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>S</i> ,6 <i>R</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-[[[(2 <i>S</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>R</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxyoxan-2-yl]oxymethyl]oxan-2-yl]oxybenzoate	

5	Hesperidin	2 <i>S</i>)-5-hydroxy-2-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-7-[(2 <i>S</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>S</i> ,6 <i>R</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-[(2 <i>R</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>R</i> ,5 <i>R</i> ,6 <i>S</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxymethyl]oxan-2-yl]oxy-2,3-dihydrochromen-4-one	
6	Punarnavoside	(2 <i>S</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,5 <i>R</i> ,9 <i>R</i> ,10 <i>R</i> ,13 <i>R</i> ,14 <i>S</i> ,17 <i>S</i>)-17-[(2 <i>R</i> ,3 <i>R</i>)-2,3-dihydroxy-6-methylheptan-2-yl]-2,14-dihydroxy-10,13-dimethyl-3-[(2 <i>R</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>S</i> ,6 <i>R</i>)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-2-yl]oxy-2,3,4,5,9,11,12,15,16,17-decahydro-1 <i>H</i> -cyclopenta[<i>a</i>]phenanthren-6-one	
7	Quercetin	2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-3,5,7-trihydroxychromen-4-one	
8	Ribavirin (standard)	1-[(2 <i>R</i> ,3 <i>R</i> ,4 <i>S</i> ,5 <i>R</i>)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)oxolan-2-yl]-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxamide	
9	Sisunatovir (Standard)	1'-[[5-(aminomethyl)-1-(4,4,4-trifluorobutyl)benzimidazol-2-yl]methyl]-6'-fluorospiro[cyclopropane-1,3'-indole]-2'-one	

Table.2- Docking, post docking analysis and Binding Free energy of Compounds with 7LVW¹¹

Ligands	Docking Score	Binding Free Energy	Interacting Residues
Chebulagic Acid	-4.192	-63.224	Leu231 ,Glu92, Thr249
Chebolic Acid	-6.273	-63.334	Ser255, Glu92, Thr249 , Apg235, Apg229
Eugenin	-4.703	-34.552	Thr249 , Tyr250,Arg229,Ser238,
Gaultherin	-4.897	-57.885	Arg 235, Glu92, Thr249
Hesperidin	-5.573	-63.610	Lys87, Asp84, Leu231, Glut92, Arg229
Punarnavoside	-4.909	-33.463	Glu92,Leu31,Asn88,Arg235,Asp84
Quercetin	-5.497	-39.207	Asn88,Thr91, Asn254.
Rosamarinic Acid	-6.57	-46.87	Asn228, Thr249 , Arg35, Tyr250,Asn88, Asn254
Sisunatovir (Standard)	-5.181	-35.062	
Ribavirin (Standard)	-4.07	-41.101	Glu92,Lys85,Asp84,Arg235

Fig.4- Interaction of Chebolic acid with 7LVW

Fig.6- Interaction of Rosamarinic Acid with 7LVW

Fig.7- Interaction of Ribavirin (standard) with 7LVW

Result of Docking Analysis-

The docking analysis of 7LVW with ligand shows significant interaction and binding affinity. Generation of good score (-1.39) site map then generation of grid and further molecular docking study shows that given ligands chebulic acid (-6.27), Hesperdin(-5.57), Rosariminic acid (-6.57) are having high docking score than ribavirin and Sisunatovir as standard drug.

B. Determination of ADME/Tox for lead compounds-

ADMET2.0 was used to determine the physicochemical parameters necessary for a drug candidates. The toxicological properties of the compounds were predicted by ADMET2.0

The Lipinski rule of five states that for a compound to be consider as a drug-like molecule.it must not be violate more than one of the following criteria : molecular weight >500DA, Octanol water partition Coefficient <5, Hydrogen bond donor ≤5, hydrogen bond acceptor ≤10. The Physicochemical Parameters calculated by ADMET2.0¹²

Table-3- Physicochemical Properties of lead Compounds¹³

Ligands	Molecular Weight	Density	Number Of Hydrogen Bond Donor	Number Of Hydrogen Bond Acceptor	Log S	Log P	Log D
Chebularic Acid	954.100	1.141	13	27	-3.57	1.220	1.515
Chebolic Acid	956.110	1.131	13	27	-3.084	1.436	0.959
Eugenin	206.060	1.021	1	4	-2.493	2.350	2.053

Gaultherin	446.140	1.098	6	12	-1.653	-0.431	-0.617
Hesperidin	610.19	1.083	8	15	-3.504	-0.59	1.156
Punarnavoside	626.37	0.997	8	11	-2.916	1.635	1.713
Quercetin	302.4	1.068	5	7	-3.671	2.155	1.767
Rosamarinic Acid	360.080	1.031	5	8	-2.432	1.775	1.650
Sisunatovir(Std)	446.170	1.063	2	5	-3.055	3.023	2.750
Ribavirin(Std)	244.080	1.163	5	9	-0.310	-2.006	-1.633

Table-4- Medicinal Chemistry of lead Compounds 14

Ligand	Lipinski rule	GSK rule	Pfizer rule	QED
Chebulagic acid	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	0.055
Chebulic acid	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	0.045
Eugenin	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	0.773
Gaultherin	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	0.246
Hesperidin	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	0.185
Punarnavoside	Rejected	Rejected	Accepted	0.187
Quercetin	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	0.434
Rosamarinic acid	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	0.298
Sisunatovir(std)	Accepted	Rejected	Rejected	0.565
Ribavirin(std)	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	0.443

Table-5- Absorption parameters of Lead Compounds 15

Ligand	Caco2 Permeability	MDCK Permeability	Bioavailability
Chebulagic Acid	-7.001	1.40E-5	1
Chebulic Acid	-7.13	2.23E-05	1
Eugenin	-4.771	1.4E-05	0.978
Gaultherin	-6.317	6.11E-05	0.993
Hesperidin	-6.484	9.40E-05	0.999
Punarnavoside	-5.074	0.000156	0.712
Quercetin	-5.204	8E-06	0.997
Rosamarinic Acid	-6.005	6.9E-06	0.994
Sisunatovir(Std)	-5.105	1.2e-05	0.003
Ribavirin(Std)	-5.582	0.00024	0.155

Table 6- Distribution Parameters of Lead Compounds 16

Ligand	Plasma Protein Binding	Volume Of Distribution	BBB Penetration
Chebulagic Acid	85.45%	0.479	0
Chebulic Acid	81.64%	0.419	0.012
Eugenin	83.95%	0.833	0.007
Gaultherin	28.25%	0.56	0.198
Hesperidin	77.64%	0.935	0.254
Punarnavoside	79.98%	0.7	0.13
Quercetin	95.49%	0.579	0.008
Rosamarinic Acid	97.72%	0.369	0.049
Sisunatovir(Std)	72.44%	2.587	0.915
Ribavirin(Std)	7.891%	0.875	0.646

Table-7-Excretion Parameters of Lead Compounds¹⁷

Ligand	Clearance	T1/2
Chebulagic Acid	6.866	0.969
Chebulic Acid	9.336	0.982
Eugenin	6.124	0.635
Gaultherin	1.053	0.788
Hesperidin	1.489	0.195
Punarnavoside	1.319	0.087
Quercetin	8.284	0.929
Rosamarinic Acid	15.347	0.959
Sisunatovir(Std)	5.081	0.127
Ribavirin(Std)	4.138	0.530

Table-8- Toxicity Parameters of Lead Compounds

Ligand	Skin Sensitization	AMES Toxicity	Carcinogenicity
Chebulagic Acid	0.706	0.045	0.01
Chebulic Acid	0.939	0.044	0.009
Eugenin	0.632	0.564	0.048
Gaultherin	0.376	0.185	0.055
Hesperidin	0.03	0.499	0.87
Punarnavoside	0.019	0.128	0.037
Quercetin	0.919	0.657	0.05
Rosamarinic Acid	0.951	0.035	0.275
Sisunatovir(Std)	0.247	0.82	0.803
Ribavirin(Std)	0.023	0.039	0.124

Result of ADMET 2.0 of lead Compounds-

The ADMET study was performed by using ADMET 2.0 software and it shows that Chebulic acid, Hesperidin and Rosamarinic acid are having high potential and shows good LogP, Log D, Bioavailability, BBB penetration and half life and Least toxicity.

CONCLUSION

Molecular docking studies, ADME/tox, were performed with 50 selected natural compounds from IBS database to evaluate prospective antiviral agents against RSV. The analysis revealed 10 top docked compounds which were further filtered by post docking analysis, Significantly Chebulic acid, Hesperidin, Rosamarinic acid it satisfied all the parameters such as docking score, glide energy, ADME/tox and trajectories analysis. We, therefore, propose that the inhibitory potentials of these ligand against 7LVW of RSV and more potential than synthetic drug such as Ribavirin and Sisunatovir This study facilitates the initiation of the RSV discovery

process for antiviral activity by using in-silico molecular Docking and ADMET study through Schrodinger and ADMET2.0.

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